

A Novel on \mathcal{NSR} Contra Strong Precontinuity

R. Narmada Devi¹, R. Dhavaseelan² and S. Jafari³

¹ Department of Mathematics, Vel Tech Rangarajan Dr. Sagunthala R & D Institute of Science and Technology, Chennai, India.

E-mail: narmadadevi23@gmail.com

² Department of Mathematics, Sona College of Technology Salem-636005, Tamil Nadu, India.

E-mail: dhavaseelan.r@gmail.com

³ Department of Mathematics, College of Vestsjaelland South, Herrestraede 11, 4200 Slagelse, Denmark.

E-mail: jafaripersia@gmail.com

*Correspondence: Author (narmadadevi23@gmail.com)

Abstract: In this paper, the concept of \mathcal{NSR} contra continuous function is introduced. Several types of contra continuous functions in \mathcal{NSR} spaces are discussed. Some interesting properties of \mathcal{NSR} contra strongly precontinuous function is established.

Keywords: \mathcal{NR} , $\mathcal{NSR} - \mathcal{CCF}$, $\mathcal{NSR} - \mathcal{C}\alpha\mathcal{CF}$, $\mathcal{NSR} - \mathcal{CpreCF}$ and $\mathcal{NSR} - \mathcal{CStrpreCF}$.

1 Introduction

L. A. Zadeh introduced the idea of fuzzy sets in 1965[16] and later Atanassov [1] generalized it and offered the concept of intuitionistic fuzzy sets. Intuitionistic fuzzy set theory has applications in many fields like medical diagnosis, information technology, nanorobotics, etc. The idea of intuitionistic L-fuzzy subring was introduced by K. Meena and V. Thomas [9]. R. Narmada Devi et al. [10, 11, 12] introduced the concept of contra strong precontinuity with respect to the intuitionistic fuzzy structure ring spaces and B. Krteska and E. Ekici [5, 7, 8] introduced the idea of intuitionistic fuzzy contra continuity. The concept of α continuity in intuitionistic fuzzy topological spaces was introduced by J. K. Jeon et al. [6]. F. Smarandache introduced the important and useful concepts of neutrosophy and neutrosophic set [[14], [15]]. A. A. Salama and S. A. Alblowi were established the concepts of neutrosophic crisp set and neutrosophic crisp topological space[13]. In this paper, the concept of \mathcal{NSR} contra continuous function is introduced. Several types of contra-continuous functions in \mathcal{NSR} spaces are discussed. Some interesting properties of \mathcal{NSR} contra strongly precontinuous function is established.

2 Preliminaries

Definition 2.1. [14, 15] Let T, I, F be real standard or non standard subsets of $]0^-, 1^+[$, with

$$(i) \sup_T = t_{sup}, \inf_T = t_{inf}$$

- (ii) $sup_I = i_{sup}, inf_I = i_{inf}$
- (iii) $sup_F = f_{sup}, inf_F = f_{inf}$
- (iv) $n - sup = t_{sup} + i_{sup} + f_{sup}$
- (v) $n - inf = t_{inf} + i_{inf} + f_{inf}$.

Observe that T, I, F are neutrosophic components.

Definition 2.2. [14, 15] Let S_1 be a non-empty fixed set. A neutrosophic set (briefly N -set) Λ is an object such that $\Lambda = \{\langle u, \mu_\Lambda(u), \sigma_\Lambda(u), \gamma_\Lambda(u) \rangle : u \in S_1\}$ where $\mu_\Lambda(u), \sigma_\Lambda(u)$ and $\gamma_\Lambda(u)$ which represents the degree of membership function (namely $\mu_\Lambda(u)$), the degree of indeterminacy (namely $\sigma_\Lambda(u)$) and the degree of non-membership (namely $\gamma_\Lambda(u)$) respectively of each element $u \in S_1$ to the set Λ .

Definition 2.3. [13] Let $S_1 \neq \emptyset$ and the N -sets Λ and Γ be defined as

$\Lambda = \{\langle u, \mu_\Lambda(u), \sigma_\Lambda(u), \Gamma_\Lambda(u) \rangle : u \in S_1\}, \Gamma = \{\langle u, \mu_\Gamma(u), \sigma_\Gamma(u), \Gamma_\Gamma(u) \rangle : u \in S_1\}$. Then

- (a) $\Lambda \subseteq \Gamma$ iff $\mu_\Lambda(u) \leq \mu_\Gamma(u), \sigma_\Lambda(u) \leq \sigma_\Gamma(u)$ and $\Gamma_\Lambda(u) \geq \Gamma_\Gamma(u)$ for all $u \in S_1$;
- (b) $\Lambda = \Gamma$ iff $\Lambda \subseteq \Gamma$ and $\Gamma \subseteq \Lambda$;
- (c) $\bar{\Lambda} = \{\langle u, \Gamma_\Lambda(u), \sigma_\Lambda(u), \mu_\Lambda(u) \rangle : u \in S_1\}$; [Complement of Λ]
- (d) $\Lambda \cap \Gamma = \{\langle u, \mu_\Lambda(u) \wedge \mu_\Gamma(u), \sigma_\Lambda(u) \wedge \sigma_\Gamma(u), \Gamma_\Lambda(u) \vee \Gamma_\Gamma(u) \rangle : u \in S_1\}$;
- (e) $\Lambda \cup \Gamma = \{\langle u, \mu_\Lambda(u) \vee \mu_\Gamma(u), \sigma_\Lambda(u) \vee \sigma_\Gamma(u), \Gamma_\Lambda(u) \wedge \Gamma_\Gamma(u) \rangle : u \in S_1\}$;
- (f) $[\]\Lambda = \{\langle u, \mu_\Lambda(u), \sigma_\Lambda(u), 1 - \mu_\Lambda(u) \rangle : u \in S_1\}$;
- (g) $\langle \rangle \Lambda = \{\langle u, 1 - \Gamma_\Lambda(u), \sigma_\Lambda(u), \Gamma_\Lambda(u) \rangle : u \in S_1\}$.

Definition 2.4. [13] Let $\{\Lambda_i : i \in J\}$ be an arbitrary family of N -sets in S_1 . Then

- (a) $\bigcap \Lambda_i = \{\langle u, \wedge \mu_{\Lambda_i}(u), \wedge \sigma_{\Lambda_i}(u), \vee \Gamma_{\Lambda_i}(u) \rangle : u \in S_1\}$;
- (b) $\bigcup \Lambda_i = \{\langle u, \vee \mu_{\Lambda_i}(u), \vee \sigma_{\Lambda_i}(u), \wedge \Gamma_{\Lambda_i}(u) \rangle : u \in S_1\}$.

Definition 2.5. [13] $0_N = \{\langle u, 0, 0, 1 \rangle : u \in S\}$ and $1_N = \{\langle u, 1, 1, 0 \rangle : u \in S\}$.

Definition 2.6. [4] A neutrosophic topology (briefly N -topology) on $S_1 \neq \emptyset$ is a family ξ_1 of N -sets in S_1 satisfying the following axioms:

- (i) $0_N, 1_N \in \xi_1$,
- (ii) $H_1 \cap H_2 \in \xi_1$ for any $H_1, H_2 \in \xi_1$,
- (iii) $\cup H_i \in \xi_1$ for arbitrary family $\{G_i \mid i \in \Lambda\} \subseteq \xi_1$.

In this case the ordered pair (S_1, ξ_1) or simply S_1 is called an NTS and each N -set in ξ_1 is called a neutrosophic open set (briefly N -open set). The complement $\bar{\Lambda}$ of an N -open set Λ in S_1 is called a neutrosophic closed set (briefly N -closed set) in S_1 .

Definition 2.7. [13] Let D be any neutrosophic set in an neutrosophic topological space S . Then the neutrosophic interior and neutrosophic closure of D are defined and denoted by

- (i) $Nint(D) = \bigcup \{H \mid H \text{ is an } NS \text{ open set in } S \text{ and } H \subseteq D\}$.
- (ii) $Ncl(D) = \bigcap \{H \mid H \text{ is a neutrosophic closed set in } S \text{ and } H \supseteq D\}$.

Proposition 2.1. [13] For any neutrosophic set D in (S, τ) we have $Ncl(C(D)) = C(Nint(D))$ and $Nint(C(D)) = C(Ncl(D))$.

Corollary 2.1. [4] Let $D, D_i (i \in J)$ and $U, U_j (j \in K)$ IFSs in be S_1 and S_2 and $\phi : S_1 \rightarrow S_2$ a function. Then

- (i) $D \subseteq \phi^{-1}(\phi(D))$ (If ϕ is injective, then $D = \phi^{-1}(\phi(D))$),
- (ii) $\phi(\phi^{-1}(U)) \subseteq U$ (If ϕ is surjective, then $\phi(\phi^{-1}(U)) = U$),
- (iii) $\phi^{-1}(\bigcup U_j) = \bigcup \phi^{-1}(U_j)$ and $\phi^{-1}(\bigcap U_j) = \bigcap \phi^{-1}(U_j)$,
- (iv) $\phi^{-1}(1_{\sim}) = 1_{\sim}$ and $\phi^{-1}(0_{\sim}) = 0_{\sim}$,
- (v) $\phi^{-1}(\overline{U}) = \overline{\phi^{-1}(U)}$.

Definition 2.8. [5]

An IFS D of an IFTS is called an intuitionistic fuzzy α -open set (IF α OS) if $D \subseteq int(cl(int(D)))$. The complement of an IF α OS is called an intuitionistic fuzzy α -closed set (IF α CS).

Definition 2.9. [3] A $\phi : X \rightarrow Y$ be a function.

- (i) If $B = \{\langle v, \mu_B(v), \gamma_B(v) \rangle : v \in Y\}$ is an IFS in Y , then the preimage of B under ϕ (denoted by $\phi^{-1}(B)$) is defined by $\phi^{-1}(B) = \{\langle u, \phi^{-1}(\mu_B)(u), \phi^{-1}(\gamma_B)(u) \rangle : u \in X\}$.
- (ii) If $A = \{\langle u, \lambda_A(u), \vartheta_A(u) \rangle : u \in X\}$ is an IFS in X , then the image of A under ϕ (denoted by $\phi(A)$) is defined by $\phi(A) = \{\langle v, \phi(\lambda_A(v)), (1 - \phi(1 - \vartheta_A))(v) \rangle : v \in Y\}$.

Definition 2.10. [3] Let (X, τ) and (Y, σ) be two IFTSs and $\phi : X \rightarrow Y$ be a function. Then ϕ is said to be intuitionistic fuzzy continuous if the preimage of each IFS in σ is an IFS in τ .

Definition 2.11. [8,9] Let R be a ring. An intuitionistic fuzzy set $A = \langle u, \mu_A, \gamma_A \rangle$ in R is called an intuitionistic fuzzy ring on R if it satisfies the following conditions:

- (i) $\mu_A(u + v) \geq \mu_A(u) \wedge \mu_A(v)$ and $\mu_A(uv) \geq \mu_A(u) \wedge \mu_A(v)$.
- (ii) $\gamma_A(u + v) \leq \gamma_A(u) \vee \gamma_A(v)$ and $\gamma_A(uv) \leq \mu_A(u) \vee \gamma_A(v)$.

for all $u, v \in R$.

3 Neutrosophic structure ring contra strong precontinuous function

In this section, the concepts of neutrosophic ring, neutrosophic structure ring space are introduced. Also some interesting properties of neutrosophic structure ring contra strong precontinuous function and their characterizations are studied.

Definition 3.1. Let \mathfrak{R} be a ring. A neutrosophic set $\Lambda = \{ \langle u, \mu_{\Lambda}(u), \sigma_{\Lambda}(u), \gamma_{\Lambda}(u) \rangle : u \in R \}$ in \mathfrak{R} is called a neutrosophic ring [briefly $\aleph\mathfrak{R}$] on \mathfrak{R} if it satisfies the following conditions:

- (i) $\mu_{\Lambda}(u+v) \geq \mu_{\Lambda}(u) \wedge \mu_{\Lambda}(v)$ and $\mu_{\Lambda}(uv) \geq \mu_{\Lambda}(u) \wedge \mu_{\Lambda}(v)$.
- (ii) $\sigma_{\Lambda}(u+v) \geq \sigma_{\Lambda}(u) \wedge \sigma_{\Lambda}(v)$ and $\sigma_{\Lambda}(uv) \geq \sigma_{\Lambda}(u) \wedge \sigma_{\Lambda}(v)$.
- (iii) $\gamma_{\Lambda}(u+v) \leq \gamma_{\Lambda}(u) \vee \gamma_{\Lambda}(v)$ and $\gamma_{\Lambda}(uv) \leq \gamma_{\Lambda}(u) \vee \gamma_{\Lambda}(v)$.

for all $u, v \in \mathfrak{R}$.

Definition 3.2. Let \mathfrak{R} be a ring. A family \mathcal{S} of a $\aleph\mathfrak{R}$'s in \mathfrak{R} is said to be neutrosophic structure ring on \mathfrak{R} if it satisfies the following axioms:

- (i) $0_N, 1_N \in \mathcal{S}$.
- (ii) $H_1 \cap H_2 \in \mathcal{S}$ for any $H_1, H_2 \in \mathcal{S}$.
- (iii) $\cup H_k \in \mathcal{S}$ for arbitrary family $\{H_k \mid k \in J\} \subseteq \mathcal{S}$.

The ordered pair $(\mathfrak{R}, \mathcal{S})$ is called a neutrosophic structure ring ($\aleph\mathfrak{SR}$) space. Every member of \mathcal{S} is called a \aleph open ring (briefly $\aleph\mathcal{OR}$) in $(\mathfrak{R}, \mathcal{S})$. The complement of a $\aleph\mathcal{OR}$ in $(\mathfrak{R}, \mathcal{S})$ is a \aleph closed ring ($\aleph\mathcal{CR}$) in $(\mathfrak{R}, \mathcal{S})$.

Definition 3.3. Let D be a \aleph ring in $\aleph\mathfrak{SR}$ space $(\mathfrak{R}, \mathcal{S})$. Then $\aleph\mathfrak{SR}$ interior and $\aleph\mathfrak{SR}$ closure of D are defined and denoted by

- (i) $\aleph\text{int}_{\mathfrak{R}}(D) = \bigcup \{H \mid H \text{ is a } \aleph\mathcal{OR} \text{ in } \mathfrak{R} \text{ and } H \subseteq D\}$.
- (ii) $\aleph\text{cl}_{\mathfrak{R}}(D) = \bigcap \{H \mid H \text{ is a } \aleph\mathcal{CR} \text{ in } \mathfrak{R} \text{ and } H \supseteq D\}$.

Proposition 3.1. For any $\aleph\mathfrak{R}$ D in $(\mathfrak{R}, \mathcal{S})$ we have

- (i) $\aleph\text{cl}_{\mathfrak{R}}(C(D)) = C(\aleph\text{int}_{\mathfrak{R}}(D))$
- (ii) $\aleph\text{int}_{\mathfrak{R}}(C(D)) = C(\aleph\text{cl}_{\mathfrak{R}}(D))$

Definition 3.4. A $\aleph\mathfrak{R}$ D of a $\aleph\mathfrak{SR}$ space $(\mathfrak{R}, \mathcal{S})$ is said to be a

- (i) \aleph regular open structure ring ($\aleph\text{RegOSR}$), if $D = \aleph\text{int}_{\mathfrak{R}}(\aleph\text{cl}_{\mathfrak{R}}(D))$
- (ii) $\aleph\alpha$ -open structure ring ($\aleph\alpha\text{OSR}$), if $D \subseteq \aleph\text{int}_{\mathfrak{R}}(\aleph\text{cl}_{\mathfrak{R}}(\aleph\text{int}_{\mathfrak{R}}(D)))$
- (iii) \aleph semiopen structure ring ($\aleph\text{SemiOSR}$), if $D \subseteq \aleph\text{cl}_{\mathfrak{R}}(\aleph\text{int}_{\mathfrak{R}}(D))$
- (iv) \aleph preopen structure ring ($\aleph\text{PreOSR}$), if $D \subseteq \aleph\text{int}_{\mathfrak{R}}(\aleph\text{cl}_{\mathfrak{R}}(D))$

(v) $\aleph\beta$ -open structure ring ($\aleph\beta\text{OSR}$), if $D \subseteq \aleph\text{cl}_{\aleph}(\aleph\text{int}_{\aleph}(\aleph\text{cl}_{\aleph}(D)))$

Note 3.1. Let (\aleph, \mathcal{S}) be a $\aleph\text{SR}$ space. Then the complement of a $\aleph\text{RegOSR}$ (resp. $\aleph\alpha\text{OSR}$, $\aleph\text{SemiOSR}$, $\aleph\text{PreOSR}$ and $\aleph\beta\text{OSR}$) is a \aleph regular closed structure ring ($\aleph\text{RegCSR}$) (resp. $\aleph\alpha$ -closed structure ring ($\aleph\alpha\text{CSR}$), \aleph semiclosed structure ring ($\aleph\text{SemiCSR}$), \aleph preclosed structure ring ($\aleph\text{PreCSR}$), $\aleph\beta$ -closed structure ring ($\aleph\beta\text{CSR}$)).

Definition 3.5. The $\aleph\text{SR}$ preinterior and $\aleph\text{SR}$ preclosure of $\aleph\aleph D$ of a $\aleph\text{SR}$ space are defined and denoted by

- (i) $\aleph\text{pint}_{\aleph}(D) = \bigcup\{H : H \text{ is a } \aleph\text{PreOSR} \text{ in } (R, \mathcal{S}) \text{ and } H \subseteq D\}$.
- (ii) $\aleph\text{pcl}_{\aleph}(D) = \bigcap\{H : H \text{ is a } \aleph\text{PreCSR} \text{ in } (R, \mathcal{S}) \text{ and } D \subseteq H\}$.

Remark 3.1. For any $\aleph\aleph D$ of a $\aleph\text{SR}$ space (\aleph, \mathcal{S}) , then

- (i) $\aleph\text{pint}_{\aleph}(D) = D$ if and only if D is a $\aleph\text{PreOSR}$.
- (ii) $\aleph\text{pcl}_{\aleph}(D) = D$ if and only if D is a $\aleph\text{PreCSR}$.
- (iii) $\aleph\text{int}_{\aleph}(D) \subseteq \aleph\text{pint}_{\aleph}(D) \subseteq D \subseteq \aleph\text{pcl}_{\aleph}(D) \subseteq \aleph\text{cl}_{\aleph}(D)$

Definition 3.6. A $\aleph\aleph D$ of a $\aleph\text{SR}$ space (\aleph, \mathcal{S}) is called a \aleph strongly preopen structure ring ($\aleph\text{stronglyPreOSR}$), if $D \subseteq \aleph\text{int}_{\aleph}(\aleph\text{pcl}_{\aleph}(D))$. The complement of a $\aleph\text{stronglyPreOSR}$ is a \aleph strongly preclosed structure ring (briefly $\aleph\text{stronglyPreCSR}$).

Definition 3.7. The $\aleph\text{SR}$ strongly preinterior and $\aleph\text{SR}$ strongly preclosure of $\aleph\aleph D$ of a $\aleph\text{SR}$ space are defined and denoted by

- (i) $\aleph\text{spint}_{\aleph}(D) = \bigcup\{H : H \text{ is a } \aleph\text{stronglyPreOSR} \text{ in } (R, \mathcal{S}) \text{ and } H \subseteq D\}$.
- (ii) $\aleph\text{spcl}_{\aleph}(D) = \bigcap\{H : H \text{ is a } \aleph\text{stronglyPreCSR} \text{ in } (R, \mathcal{S}) \text{ and } D \subseteq H\}$.

Remark 3.2. For any $\aleph\aleph D$ of a $\aleph\text{SR}$ space (\aleph, \mathcal{S}) , then

- (i) $\aleph\text{spint}_{\aleph}(D) = D$ if and only if D is a $\aleph\text{stronglyPreOSR}$.
- (ii) $\aleph\text{spcl}_{\aleph}(D) = D$ if and only if D is a $\aleph\text{stronglyPreCSR}$.
- (iii) $\aleph\text{int}_{\aleph}(D) \subseteq \aleph\text{spint}_{\aleph}(D) \subseteq D \subseteq \aleph\text{spcl}_{\aleph}(D) \subseteq \aleph\text{cl}_{\aleph}(D)$

Proposition 3.2. A $\aleph\aleph$ of a $\aleph\text{SR}$ space (\aleph, \mathcal{S}) is a $\aleph\alpha\text{OSR}$ if and only if it is both $\aleph\text{SemiOSR}$ and $\aleph\text{stronglyPreOSR}$.

Definition 3.8. Let $(\aleph_1, \mathcal{S}_1)$ and $(\aleph_2, \mathcal{S}_2)$ be any two $\aleph\text{SR}$ spaces. A function $\phi : (\aleph_1, \mathcal{S}_1) \rightarrow (\aleph_2, \mathcal{S}_2)$ is called a $\aleph\text{SR}$

- (i) contra continuous function ($\aleph\text{SR} - \mathcal{CCF}$) if $\phi^{-1}(U)$ is a $\aleph\text{OR}$ in $(\aleph_1, \mathcal{S}_1)$, for each $\aleph\text{CR } U$ in $(\aleph_2, \mathcal{S}_2)$.
- (ii) contra α -continuous function ($\aleph\text{SR} - \mathcal{C}\alpha\mathcal{CF}$) if $\phi^{-1}(U)$ is a $\aleph\alpha\text{OR}$ in $(\aleph_1, \mathcal{S}_1)$, for each $\aleph\text{CR } U$ in $(\aleph_2, \mathcal{S}_2)$.
- (iii) contra precontinuous function ($\aleph\text{SR} - \mathcal{CpreCF}$) if $\phi^{-1}(U)$ is a $\aleph\text{PreOSR}$ in $(\aleph_1, \mathcal{S}_1)$, for each $\aleph\text{CR } U$ in $(\aleph_2, \mathcal{S}_2)$.

(iv) contra strongly precontinuous function ($\mathfrak{NSR} - \mathfrak{CStrpreCF}$) if $\phi^{-1}(U)$ is a $\mathfrak{NstronglyPreOSR}$ in $(\mathfrak{R}_1, \mathcal{S}_1)$, for each $\mathfrak{NCR} U$ in $(\mathfrak{R}_2, \mathcal{S}_2)$.

Proposition 3.3. Let $(\mathfrak{R}_1, \mathcal{S}_1)$ and $(\mathfrak{R}_2, \mathcal{S}_2)$ be any two \mathfrak{NSR} spaces. Let $\phi : (\mathfrak{R}_1, \mathcal{S}_1) \rightarrow (\mathfrak{R}_2, \mathcal{S}_2)$ be a function. If ϕ is a $\mathfrak{NSR} - \mathfrak{CCF}$, then ϕ is a $\mathfrak{NSR} - \mathfrak{C}\alpha\mathfrak{CF}$.

Proof:

Let U be a \mathfrak{NCR} in $(\mathfrak{R}_2, \mathcal{S}_2)$. Since ϕ is $\mathfrak{NSR} - \mathfrak{CCF}$, $\phi^{-1}(U)$ is a \mathfrak{NOR} in $(\mathfrak{R}_1, \mathcal{S}_1)$, for each $\mathfrak{NCR} U$ in $(\mathfrak{R}_2, \mathcal{S}_2)$. By Remark 3.1(iii), $\phi^{-1}(U) \subseteq \mathfrak{Ncl}_{\mathfrak{R}_1}(\phi^{-1}(U))$.

Since $\phi^{-1}(U)$ is a \mathfrak{NOR} in $(\mathfrak{R}_1, \mathcal{S}_1)$, $\phi^{-1}(U) \subseteq \mathfrak{Ncl}_{\mathfrak{R}_1}(\mathfrak{Nint}_{\mathfrak{R}_1}(\phi^{-1}(U)))$. Hence, $\phi^{-1}(U)$ is a $\mathfrak{NSemiOSR}$ in $(\mathfrak{R}_1, \mathcal{S}_1)$. By Remark 3.1 (iii), $\phi^{-1}(U) \subseteq \mathfrak{Npcl}_{\mathfrak{R}_1}(\phi^{-1}(U))$. Taking interior on both sides, $\mathfrak{Nint}_{\mathfrak{R}_1}(\phi^{-1}(U)) \subseteq \mathfrak{Nint}_{\mathfrak{R}_1}(\mathfrak{Npcl}_{\mathfrak{R}_1}(\phi^{-1}(U)))$. Since $\phi^{-1}(U)$ is a \mathfrak{NOR} in $(\mathfrak{R}_1, \mathcal{S}_1)$, $\phi^{-1}(U) \subseteq \mathfrak{Nint}_{\mathfrak{R}_1}(\mathfrak{Npcl}_{\mathfrak{R}_1}(\phi^{-1}(U)))$. Hence, $\phi^{-1}(U)$ is a $\mathfrak{NstronglyPreOSR}$ in $(\mathfrak{R}_1, \mathcal{S}_1)$. Therefore, $\phi^{-1}(U)$ is both $\mathfrak{NSemiOSR}$ and $\mathfrak{NstronglyPreOSR}$ in $(\mathfrak{R}_1, \mathcal{S}_1)$. By Proposition 3.1, $\phi^{-1}(\phi)$ is a $\mathfrak{N}\alpha\mathfrak{OSR}$ in $(\mathfrak{R}_1, \mathcal{S}_1)$, for each $\mathfrak{NCR} U$ in $(\mathfrak{R}_2, \mathcal{S}_2)$. Hence, ϕ is a $\mathfrak{NSR} - \mathfrak{C}\alpha\mathfrak{CF}$.

Proposition 3.4. Let $(\mathfrak{R}_1, \mathcal{S}_1)$ and $(\mathfrak{R}_2, \mathcal{S}_2)$ be any two \mathfrak{NSR} spaces. Let $\phi : (\mathfrak{R}_1, \mathcal{S}_1) \rightarrow (\mathfrak{R}_2, \mathcal{S}_2)$ be a function. If ϕ is a $\mathfrak{NSR} - \mathfrak{C}\alpha\mathfrak{CF}$, then ϕ is a $\mathfrak{NSR} - \mathfrak{CStrpreCF}$.

Proof:

Let U be any \mathfrak{NCR} in $(\mathfrak{R}_2, \mathcal{S}_2)$. Since ϕ is a $\mathfrak{NSR} - \mathfrak{C}\alpha\mathfrak{CF}$, $\phi^{-1}(U)$ is a $\mathfrak{N}\alpha\mathfrak{OSR}$ in $(\mathfrak{R}_1, \mathcal{S}_1)$, for each $\mathfrak{NCR} U$ in $(\mathfrak{R}_2, \mathcal{S}_2)$. By Proposition 3.1, $\phi^{-1}(U)$ is both $\mathfrak{NSemiOSR}$ and $\mathfrak{NstronglyPreOSR}$ in $(\mathfrak{R}_1, \mathcal{S}_1)$, for each $\mathfrak{NCR} U$ in $(\mathfrak{R}_2, \mathcal{S}_2)$. Therefore, $\phi^{-1}(U)$ is a $\mathfrak{NstronglyPreOSR}$ in $(\mathfrak{R}_1, \mathcal{S}_1)$, for each $\mathfrak{NCR} U$ in $(\mathfrak{R}_2, \mathcal{S}_2)$. Hence ϕ is a $\mathfrak{NSR} - \mathfrak{CStrpreCF}$.

Proposition 3.5. Let $(\mathfrak{R}_1, \mathcal{S}_1)$ and $(\mathfrak{R}_2, \mathcal{S}_2)$ be any two \mathfrak{NSR} spaces. Let $\phi : (\mathfrak{R}_1, \mathcal{S}_1) \rightarrow (\mathfrak{R}_2, \mathcal{S}_2)$ be a function. If ϕ is a $\mathfrak{NSR} - \mathfrak{CStrpreCF}$, then ϕ is a $\mathfrak{NSR} - \mathfrak{CpreCF}$.

Proof:

Let U be any \mathfrak{NCR} in $(\mathfrak{R}_2, \mathcal{S}_2)$. Since ϕ is a $\mathfrak{NSR} - \mathfrak{CStrpreCF}$, $\phi^{-1}(U)$ is a $\mathfrak{NstronglyPreOSR}$ in $(\mathfrak{R}_1, \mathcal{S}_1)$, for each $\mathfrak{NCR} U$ in $(\mathfrak{R}_2, \mathcal{S}_2)$, that is,

$$\phi^{-1}(U) \subseteq \mathfrak{Nint}_{\mathfrak{R}_1}(\mathfrak{Npcl}_{\mathfrak{R}_1}(\phi^{-1}(U))) \quad (3.1)$$

By Remark 3.1(iii),

$$\mathfrak{Npcl}_{\mathfrak{R}_1}(\phi^{-1}(U)) \subseteq \mathfrak{Ncl}_{\mathfrak{R}_1}(\phi^{-1}(U)) \quad (3.2)$$

Substitute (3.2) in (3.1), we get $\phi^{-1}(U) \subseteq \mathfrak{Nint}_{\mathfrak{R}_1}(\mathfrak{Ncl}_{\mathfrak{R}_1}(\phi^{-1}(U)))$. Therefore, $\phi^{-1}(U)$ is a $\mathfrak{NPreOSR}$ in $(\mathfrak{R}_1, \mathcal{S}_1)$, for each $\mathfrak{NCR} U$ in $(\mathfrak{R}_2, \mathcal{S}_2)$. Hence, ϕ is a $\mathfrak{NSR} - \mathfrak{CpreCF}$.

Proposition 3.6. Let $(\mathfrak{R}_1, \mathcal{S}_1)$ and $(\mathfrak{R}_2, \mathcal{S}_2)$ be any two \mathfrak{NSR} spaces. Let $\phi : (\mathfrak{R}_1, \mathcal{S}_1) \rightarrow (\mathfrak{R}_2, \mathcal{S}_2)$ be a function. If ϕ is a $\mathfrak{NSR} - \mathfrak{CCF}$, then ϕ is a $\mathfrak{NSR} - \mathfrak{CStrpreCF}$.

Proof:

Let U be any \mathfrak{NCR} in $(\mathfrak{R}_2, \mathcal{S}_2)$. Since ϕ is a $\mathfrak{NSR} - \mathfrak{CCF}$, $\phi^{-1}(U)$ is a \mathfrak{NOR} in $(\mathfrak{R}_1, \mathcal{S}_1)$, for each $\mathfrak{NCR} U$ in $(\mathfrak{R}_2, \mathcal{S}_2)$, that is, $\phi^{-1}(U) = \mathfrak{Nint}_{\mathfrak{R}_1}(\phi^{-1}(U))$. By Remark 3.1(iii),

$$\phi^{-1}(U) \subseteq \mathfrak{Npcl}_{\mathfrak{R}_1}(\phi^{-1}(U)) \quad (3.3)$$

Taking interior on both sides in (3.3),

$$\phi^{-1}(U) = \mathfrak{Nint}_{\mathfrak{R}_1}(\phi^{-1}(U)) \subseteq \mathfrak{Nint}_{\mathfrak{R}_1}(\mathfrak{Npcl}_{\mathfrak{R}_1}(\phi^{-1}(U))).$$

Hence, $\phi^{-1}(U)$ is a \aleph stronglyPreOS \aleph in $(\aleph_1, \mathcal{S}_1)$, for each \aleph CR U in $(\aleph_2, \mathcal{S}_2)$. Thus, ϕ is a \aleph SR – $\mathcal{C}Strpre\mathcal{CF}$.

Proposition 3.7. Let $(\aleph_1, \mathcal{S}_1)$ and $(\aleph_2, \mathcal{S}_2)$ be any two \aleph SR spaces. Let $\phi : (\aleph_1, \mathcal{S}_1) \rightarrow (\aleph_2, \mathcal{S}_2)$ be a function. If ϕ is a \aleph SR – \mathcal{CCF} , then ϕ is a \aleph SR – \mathcal{CpreCF} .

Proof:

Let U be any \aleph CR in $(\aleph_2, \mathcal{S}_2)$. Since ϕ is a \aleph SR – \mathcal{CCF} , $\phi^{-1}(U)$ is a \aleph OR in $(\aleph_1, \mathcal{S}_1)$, for each \aleph CR U in $(\aleph_2, \mathcal{S}_2)$, that is, $\phi^{-1}(U) = \aleph int_{\aleph_1}(\phi^{-1}(U))$. By Remark 3.1(iii),

$$\phi^{-1}(B) \subseteq \aleph cl_{\aleph_1}(\phi^{-1}(U)) \tag{3.4}$$

Taking interior on both sides in (3.4),

$$\phi^{-1}(U) = \aleph int_{\aleph_1}(\phi^{-1}(U)) \subseteq \aleph int_{\aleph_1}(\aleph cl_{\aleph_1}(\phi^{-1}(U))).$$

Hence, $\phi^{-1}(U)$ is a \aleph PreOS \aleph in $(\aleph_1, \mathcal{S}_1)$, for each \aleph CR U in $(\aleph_2, \mathcal{S}_2)$. Thus, ϕ is a \aleph SR – \mathcal{CpreCF} .

Remark 3.3. The converses of the Proposition 3.2, Proposition 3.3, Proposition 3.4, Proposition 3.5 and Proposition 3.6 need not be true as it is shown in the following example.

Example 3.1. Let $\aleph = \{a, b, c\}$ be a nonempty set with two binary operations as follows:

+	u	v	w
u	u	v	w
v	v	w	u
w	w	u	v

and

*	u	v	w
u	u	u	u
v	u	v	w
w	u	w	v

Then $(\aleph, +, *)$ is a ring. Define \aleph R's L, M and P as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \mu_L(u) &= 0.4, \mu_L(v) = 0.8, \mu_L(w) = 0.2; \\ \mu_M(u) &= 0.7, \mu_M(v) = 0.9, \mu_M(w) = 0.4; \\ \mu_P(u) &= 0.5, \mu_P(v) = 0.7, \mu_P(w) = 0.3; \\ \sigma_L(u) &= 0.4, \sigma_L(v) = 0.8, \sigma_L(w) = 0.2; \\ \sigma_M(u) &= 0.7, \sigma_M(v) = 0.9, \sigma_M(w) = 0.4; \\ \sigma_P(u) &= 0.5, \sigma_P(v) = 0.7, \sigma_P(w) = 0.3; \\ \gamma_L(u) &= 0.1, \gamma_L(v) = 0.1, \gamma_L(w) = 0.1; \\ \gamma_M(u) &= 0.1, \gamma_M(v) = 0.1, \gamma_M(w) = 0.1; \text{ and} \\ \gamma_P(u) &= 0.1, \gamma_P(v) = 0.1, \gamma_P(w) = 0.1. \end{aligned}$$

Then $\mathcal{S}_1 = \{0_N, 1_N, L, M\}$, $\mathcal{S}_2 = \{0_N, 1_N, P\}$, $\mathcal{S}_3 = \{0_N, 1_N, C(L)\}$ and $\mathcal{S}_4 = \{0_N, 1_N, P\}$ are the \aleph SR's on \aleph .

Then the identity function $\phi : (\aleph, \mathcal{S}_2) \rightarrow (\aleph, \mathcal{S}_3)$ is a \aleph SR – \mathcal{CpreCF} , but ϕ is neither \aleph SR – \mathcal{CCF} nor \aleph SR – $\mathcal{C}Strpre\mathcal{CF}$.

Similarly the identity function $\phi : (\mathfrak{R}, \mathcal{S}_1) \rightarrow (\mathfrak{R}, \mathcal{S}_4)$ is a $\mathfrak{NSR} - \mathfrak{CStrpreCF}$ but ϕ is neither $\mathfrak{NSR} - \mathfrak{CCF}$ nor $\mathfrak{NSR} - \mathfrak{CaCF}$

Remark 3.4. Clearly the following diagram holds.

Proposition 3.8. Let $(\mathfrak{R}_1, \mathcal{S}_1)$ and $(\mathfrak{R}_2, \mathcal{S}_2)$ be any two \mathfrak{NSR} spaces. Let $\phi : (\mathfrak{R}_1, \mathcal{S}_1) \rightarrow (\mathfrak{R}_2, \mathcal{S}_2)$ be a function. Then the following are equivalent.

- (i) ϕ is $\mathfrak{NSR} - \mathfrak{CStrpreCF}$.
- (ii) $\phi^{-1}(U)$ is a $\mathfrak{NstronglyPreCSR}$ in $(\mathfrak{R}_1, \mathcal{S}_1)$, for each \mathfrak{NOR} U in $(\mathfrak{R}_2, \mathcal{S}_2)$.

Proof:

(i) \Rightarrow (ii)

Let U be any \mathfrak{NOR} in $(\mathfrak{R}_2, \mathcal{S}_2)$, then $C(U)$ is a \mathfrak{NCR} in $(\mathfrak{R}_2, \mathcal{S}_2)$. Since ϕ is a $\mathfrak{NSR} - \mathfrak{CStrpreCF}$, $\phi^{-1}(C(U))$ is a $\mathfrak{NstronglyPreOSR}$ in $(\mathfrak{R}_1, \mathcal{S}_1)$, for each \mathfrak{NCR} $C(U)$ in $(\mathfrak{R}_2, \mathcal{S}_2)$. By Remark 3.2(i), $\phi^{-1}(C(U)) = C(\phi^{-1}(U)) \subseteq \mathfrak{Nint}_{\mathfrak{R}_1}(\mathfrak{Npcl}_{\mathfrak{R}_1}(C(\phi^{-1}(U))))$. Therefore, $\phi^{-1}(U)$ is a $\mathfrak{NstronglyPreCSR}$ in $(\mathfrak{R}_1, \mathcal{S}_1)$, for each \mathfrak{NOR} U in $(\mathfrak{R}_2, \mathcal{S}_2)$.

(ii) \Rightarrow (i)

Let $C(U)$ be any \mathfrak{NOR} in $(\mathfrak{R}_2, \mathcal{S}_2)$. Then U is a \mathfrak{NCR} in $(\mathfrak{R}_2, \mathcal{S}_2)$. Since $\phi^{-1}(C(U))$ is a $\mathfrak{NstronglyPreCSR}$ in $(\mathfrak{R}_1, \mathcal{S}_1)$, for each \mathfrak{NOR} $C(U)$ in $(\mathfrak{R}_2, \mathcal{S}_2)$. We have, $\phi^{-1}(U)$ is a $\mathfrak{NstronglyPreOSR}$ in $(\mathfrak{R}_1, \mathcal{S}_1)$, for each \mathfrak{NCR} U in $(\mathfrak{R}_2, \mathcal{S}_2)$. Hence, ϕ is a $\mathfrak{NSR} - \mathfrak{CStrpreCF}$.

Proposition 3.9. Let $(\mathfrak{R}_1, \mathcal{S}_1)$ and $(\mathfrak{R}_2, \mathcal{S}_2)$ be any two \mathfrak{NSR} spaces. Let $\phi : (\mathfrak{R}_1, \mathcal{S}_1) \rightarrow (\mathfrak{R}_2, \mathcal{S}_2)$ be a function. Suppose if one of the following statement hold.

- (i) $\phi^{-1}(\mathfrak{Ncl}_{\mathfrak{R}_2}(V)) \subseteq \mathfrak{Nint}_{\mathfrak{R}_1}(\mathfrak{Npcl}_{\mathfrak{R}_1}(\phi^{-1}(V)))$, for each \mathfrak{NR} V in $(\mathfrak{R}_2, \mathcal{S}_2)$.
- (ii) $\mathfrak{Ncl}_{\mathfrak{R}_1}(\mathfrak{Npint}_{\mathfrak{R}_1}(\phi^{-1}(V))) \subseteq \phi^{-1}(\mathfrak{Nint}_{\mathfrak{R}_2}(V))$, for each \mathfrak{NR} V in $(\mathfrak{R}_2, \mathcal{S}_2)$.
- (iii) $\phi(\mathfrak{Ncl}_{\mathfrak{R}_1}(\mathfrak{Npint}_{\mathfrak{R}_1}(V))) \subseteq \mathfrak{Nint}_{\mathfrak{R}_2}(\phi(V))$, for each \mathfrak{NR} V in $(\mathfrak{R}_1, \mathcal{S}_1)$.
- (iv) $\phi(\mathfrak{Ncl}_{\mathfrak{R}_1}(V)) \subseteq \mathfrak{Nint}_{\mathfrak{R}_2}(\phi(V))$, for each $\mathfrak{NPreOSR}$ V in $(\mathfrak{R}_1, \mathcal{S}_1)$.

Then, ϕ is a $\mathfrak{NSR} - \mathfrak{CStrpreCF}$.

Proof:

(i) \Rightarrow (ii)

Let U be any \mathfrak{NR} in $(\mathfrak{R}_2, \mathcal{S}_2)$. Then, $\phi^{-1}(\mathfrak{Ncl}_{\mathfrak{R}_2}(U)) \subseteq \mathfrak{Nint}_{\mathfrak{R}_1}(\mathfrak{Npcl}_{\mathfrak{R}_1}(\phi^{-1}(U)))$ By taking complement on both sides,

$$C(\mathfrak{Nint}_{\mathfrak{R}_1}(\mathfrak{Npcl}_{\mathfrak{R}_1}(\phi^{-1}(U)))) \subseteq C(\phi^{-1}(\mathfrak{Ncl}_{\mathfrak{R}_2}(U)))$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathfrak{N}cl_{\mathfrak{R}_1}(C(\mathfrak{N}pcl_{\mathfrak{R}_1}(\phi^{-1}(U)))) &\subseteq \phi^{-1}(C(\mathfrak{N}cl_{\mathfrak{R}_2}(U))) \\ \mathfrak{N}cl_{\mathfrak{R}_1}(\mathfrak{N}pint_{\mathfrak{R}_1}(C(\phi^{-1}(U)))) &\subseteq \phi^{-1}(\mathfrak{N}int_{\mathfrak{R}_2}(C(U))) \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, $\mathfrak{N}cl_{\mathfrak{R}_1}(\mathfrak{N}pint_{\mathfrak{R}_1}(\phi^{-1}(V))) \subseteq \phi^{-1}(\mathfrak{N}int_{\mathfrak{R}_2}(V))$, for each $\mathfrak{N}\mathfrak{R} V = C(U)$ in $(\mathfrak{R}_2, \mathcal{S}_2)$.

(ii)⇒(iii)

Let U be any $\mathfrak{N}\mathfrak{R}$ in $(\mathfrak{R}_2, \mathcal{S}_2)$. Let V be any $\mathfrak{N}\mathfrak{R}$ in $(\mathfrak{R}_1, \mathcal{S}_1)$ such that $U = \phi(V)$. Then $V \subseteq \phi^{-1}(U)$. By (ii), $\mathfrak{N}cl_{\mathfrak{R}_1}(\mathfrak{N}pint_{\mathfrak{R}_1}(\phi^{-1}(U))) \subseteq \phi^{-1}(\mathfrak{N}int_{\mathfrak{R}_2}(U))$. We have

$$\mathfrak{N}cl_{\mathfrak{R}_1}(\mathfrak{N}pint_{\mathfrak{R}_1}(V)) \subseteq \mathfrak{N}cl_{\mathfrak{R}_1}(\mathfrak{N}pint_{\mathfrak{R}_1}(\phi^{-1}(U))) \subseteq \phi^{-1}(\mathfrak{N}int_{\mathfrak{R}_2}(\phi(V)))$$

Therefore, $\phi(\mathfrak{N}cl_{\mathfrak{R}_1}(\mathfrak{N}pint_{\mathfrak{R}_1}(V))) \subseteq \mathfrak{N}int_{\mathfrak{R}_2}(\phi(V))$, for each $\mathfrak{N}\mathfrak{R} V$ in $(\mathfrak{R}_1, \mathcal{S}_1)$.

(iii)⇒(iv)

Let V be any $\mathfrak{N}Pre\mathfrak{OS}\mathfrak{R}$ in $(\mathfrak{R}_1, \mathcal{S}_1)$. Then $\mathfrak{N}pint_{\mathfrak{R}_1}(V) = V$. By (iii),

$$\phi(\mathfrak{N}cl_{\mathfrak{R}_1}(\mathfrak{N}pint_{\mathfrak{R}_1}(V))) = \phi(\mathfrak{N}cl_{\mathfrak{R}_1}(V)) \subseteq \mathfrak{N}int_{\mathfrak{R}_2}(\phi(V)).$$

Therefore, $\phi(\mathfrak{N}cl_{\mathfrak{R}_1}(V)) \subseteq \mathfrak{N}int_{\mathfrak{R}_2}(\phi(V))$, for each $\mathfrak{N}Pre\mathfrak{OS}\mathfrak{R} V$ in $(\mathfrak{R}_1, \mathcal{S}_1)$.

Suppose that (iv) holds. Let U be any $\mathfrak{N}\mathfrak{O}\mathfrak{R}$ in $(\mathfrak{R}_2, \mathcal{S}_2)$. Then $\mathfrak{N}pint_{\mathfrak{R}_1}(\phi^{-1}(U))$ is a $\mathfrak{N}Pre\mathfrak{OS}\mathfrak{R}$ in $(\mathfrak{R}_1, \mathcal{S}_1)$. By (iv),

$$\begin{aligned} \phi(\mathfrak{N}cl_{\mathfrak{R}_1}(\mathfrak{N}pint_{\mathfrak{R}_1}(\phi^{-1}(U)))) &\subseteq \mathfrak{N}int_{\mathfrak{R}_2}(\phi(\mathfrak{N}pint_{\mathfrak{R}_1}(\phi^{-1}(U)))) \\ &\subseteq \mathfrak{N}int_{\mathfrak{R}_2}(\phi(\phi^{-1}(U))) \subseteq \mathfrak{N}int_{\mathfrak{R}_2}(U) = U. \end{aligned}$$

We have, $\phi^{-1}(\phi(\mathfrak{N}cl_{\mathfrak{R}_1}(\mathfrak{N}pint_{\mathfrak{R}_1}(\phi^{-1}(U)))) \subseteq \phi^{-1}(U)$.

Then $\mathfrak{N}cl_{\mathfrak{R}_1}(\mathfrak{N}pint_{\mathfrak{R}_1}(\phi^{-1}(U))) \subseteq \phi^{-1}(U)$. This implies that $\phi^{-1}(U)$ is a $\mathfrak{N}Pre\mathfrak{CS}\mathfrak{R}$ in $(\mathfrak{R}_1, \mathcal{S}_1)$. Taking complement on both sides, $C(\phi^{-1}(U)) \subseteq C(\mathfrak{N}cl_{\mathfrak{R}_1}(\mathfrak{N}pint_{\mathfrak{R}_1}(\phi^{-1}(U))))$. This implies that $\phi^{-1}(C(U)) \subseteq \mathfrak{N}int_{\mathfrak{R}_1}(\mathfrak{N}pcl_{\mathfrak{R}_1}(\phi^{-1}(C(U))))$. Therefore $\phi^{-1}(C(U))$ is a $\mathfrak{N}stronglyPre\mathfrak{OS}\mathfrak{R}$ in $(\mathfrak{R}_1, \mathcal{S}_1)$, for each $\mathfrak{N}\mathfrak{C}\mathfrak{R} C(U)$ in $(\mathfrak{R}_2, \mathcal{S}_2)$. Hence, ϕ is a $\mathfrak{N}\mathfrak{S}\mathfrak{R} - \mathfrak{C}Strpre\mathfrak{C}\mathcal{F}$.

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Received: January 22 2019. Accepted: March 20, 2019